

Postindustrial frameworks: beginning design studies in the third age of production

Leonard Bachman
The University of Houston
Gerald D. Hines College of Architecture

Postindustrial frameworks: beginning design studies in the third age of production

Leonard Bachman
The University of Houston
Gerald D. Hines College of Architecture

Postindustrial frameworks: beginning design studies in the third age of production

Leonard Bachman
The University of Houston
Gerald D. Hines College of Architecture

FOUR QUESTIONS

1. Postindustrial?
2. Complexity?
3. Systems?
4. The Problem?

FOUR ASSERTIONS

1. Aesthetics!
2. Cognition!
3. Hermeneutics!
4. Design!

OUTLINE (against a blue sky)

Share of total employment in manufacturing and services sectors, 1965 and 2005

* QUESTION 1: Postindustrial?

POSTINDUSTRIAL ≈ COMPLEXITY ≈ SYSTEMS ≈ THE PROBLEM
 AESTHETICS ≈ COGNITION ≈ HERMENEUTICS ≈ DESIGN

- * From Goods to Services
- * Knowledge Work
- * Information Society
- * Systems Understanding
- * Transdisciplinary Teams

POSTINDUSTRIAL SOCIETY: from mechanistic to organic

Techne: Ideals and Means of Production as a Story about Civilization

Geddes 1915	Mumford 1934	Fourastié 1975	Bell 1973
EOTECHNIC: Life in Balance -Raw material production	EOTECHNIC- 1000 to 1700 -Village life, coal and steel -Intensification of life	PRIMARY: Traditional 70-20-10	PREINDUSTRIAL -Agriculture and mining -Raw material basis of production
PALEOTECHNIC: Life Threatened -Private dispensation of resources -Resources for individual gain	PALEOTECHNIC- 1700 to 1900 -Industrial Megapolis -Profit overrides general principles	SECONDARY Trente Glorieuses 20-50-30	INDUSTRIAL -Practical know-how -Productive labor
EUTECHNIC- Life Resurgent -Public conservation of resources -Evolution of public good, social equity	NEOTECHNIC- 1934 forward -Organic human scale living -Science, communication, information	TERTIARY 10-20-70 -Education, culture, social equity	POSTINDUSTRIAL -Human capital, automation -Intellectual technology, network society

<i>Craft, Machine, and System: the Technical Epochs of Design</i>	PRE INDUSTRIAL Before about 1700 The Eotechnic	INDUSTRIAL About 1700 to the present The Paleotechnic	POST INDUSTRIAL The evolving present The Neotechnic
Design	Craft and design are synonymous	Design as a specialty and a profession	Design as a discipline and universal occupation
Materials	Raw materials directly from nature	Processed material and mass standardization	Mass customization of components and materials
Knowledge base	Static	Incremental shifts	Continuous change
Cosmology	Mythical explanations	Anthropocentric	Biocentric
Order	Holistic	Heirarchical	Holistic
Development	Refine the prototype	Test unique artifact	Simulate possible artifacts
Change	Conformity	Novelty	Evolutionary
Instrument	Nature as the model	Drawings	Virtual simulations
Method	Normative rules and traditions	Methods and procedures	Cybernetic knowledge and systems integration
Perspective	Holistic	Components in isolation	Integrated systems
Dynamics	Innocent naievity	Self referential	Intelligent
Lifecycle	Degrade	Use and dispose	Reprocess as nutrient
Solutions	Transient	Fragile and fragmentary	Robust
Effort	Communal	Individual	Team
Educate	Trade apprentice	University: liberal pupilage	Explicit and synthetic
Collaboration	Monodisciplinary guilds	Multidisciplinary	Transdisciplinary
Application	Need	Art for the elite	Sustain societal goals

Wicked Problems (Rittel)

- * No problem space
- * No operating rules
- * No finishing rules
- * Moving target

Fertile Ambiguity

Limited Cognition (Simon)

Indeterminate

Dynamic

* QUESTION 3: Complexity?

POSTINDUSTRIAL ≈ COMPLEXITY ≈ SYSTEMS ≈ THE PROBLEM
AESTHETICS ≈ COGNITION ≈ HERMENEUTICS ≈ DESIGN

“PLC” AND “PLEX” (Rzevski)

10

2/27/2015 10:13:42 AM

- * Organized flow
- * Emergent order
- * Self regulating
- * Non Linear
- * Non Deterministic
- * Non Mechanistic (a forest rather than a tree farm)
- * Deep Interrelatedness
- * Purposeful
- * Powered by Entropy or Information

* QUESTION 3: Systems?

POSTINDUSTRIAL ≈ COMPLEXITY ≈ **SYSTEMS** ≈ THE PROBLEM
 AESTHETICS ≈ COGNITION ≈ HERMENEUTICS ≈ DESIGN

- * Bimodal-seasonal, diurnal, occupancy...
- * Organized flow-people, air, light, product, information (Groak 2002)...
- * Interactive
- * Dynamic

* Buildings are organisms /systems

1. Theory over expertise
2. Transdisciplinary over hero
3. Evidence over intuition
4. Parametric exploration
5. Clinical practice
6. Cultural AND social bases
7. Shared authorship
8. Physical AND strategic
9. Short-termism vs. sustainable
10. Public trust
11. Corporate management

*QUESTION 4: The Problem?

POSTINDUSTRIAL≈COMPLEXITY≈SYSTEMS≈**THE PROBLEM**
AESTHETICS≈COGNITION≈HERMENEUTICS≈DESIGN

* ASSERTION 1: Aesthetics

POSTINDUSTRIAL ≈ COMPLEXITY ≈ SYSTEMS ≈ THE PROBLEM
AESTHETICS ≈ COGNITION ≈ HERMENEUTICS ≈ DESIGN

*Gadamer: The ontological function of beauty is to bridge the chasm between the **real** and the **ideal**

*Scrutton: Aesthetics conveys the interdependence of our understanding **[real]** and our appreciation **[ideal]**

*Kahn: ...the measureable **[real]** and the immeasurable **[ideal]**...

AESTHETICS

Left Brain
Strategic Aspect

Effect

Foresight

Intelligence

Rational

Measureable

The Real

Right Brain
Physical Aspect

Affect

Immediacy

Significance

Emotive

Immeasurable

The Ideal

*** ASSERTION 2: Cognition**

POSTINDUSTRIAL ≈ COMPLEXITY ≈ SYSTEMS ≈ THE PROBLEM

AESTHETICS ≈ **COGNITION** ≈ HERMENEUTICS ≈ DESIGN

Left Brain:
Erectorheads

Right Brain:
Designosaurs

TWO SPHERES

PHYSICAL DESIGN AS SUBLIME IMMEDIACY

STRATEGIC DESIGN AS INTELLIGENT FORESIGHT

CONFLUENCE

2/27/2015 10:13:42 AM

CONSILIENCE

POPPER'S THREE WORLD MODEL

Gadamer: The ontological function of beauty is to bridge the chasm between the real and the ideal

* ASSERTION 3: Hermeneutic Abduction

POSTINDUSTRIAL ≈ COMPLEXITY ≈ SYSTEMS ≈ THE PROBLEM
AESTHETICS ≈ COGNITION ≈ **HERMENEUTICS** ≈ DESIGN

Hermeneutics

divergent

* ASSERTION 4: Design

POSTINDUSTRIAL ≈ COMPLEXITY ≈ SYSTEMS ≈ THE PROBLEM
AESTHETICS ≈ COGNITION ≈ HERMENEUTICS ≈ **DESIGN**

DESIGN INQUIRY AND RESEARCH INQUIRY

LINEAR MODELS OF DESIGN AND RESEARCH

DESIGN

- 1 Theory building
- 2 Programming
- 3 Parti or Architectural intent
- 4 Client
- 5 Society
- 6 Precedent buildings, history
- 7 Process of resolution
- 8 Wicked indeterminant problems
- 9 Design development
- 10 Critics, cultural evaluation
- 11 Architectural journal publication
- 12 Accepted as innovation
- 13 "Accumulated wisdom of architecture"
- 14 Many scales of acheivement
- 15 Ocassional new prototype
- 16 Leads toward new theories

RESEARCH

- Theory building
- Understanding the problem
- Hypothesis, the research question
- Funding agency
- Cultural contribution, long term
- Existing knowledge base
- Method of investigation
- Open ended
- Strategies and techniques
- Expert reviewers, truth value
- Peer reviewed journals
- Validity and reliability
- New useful knowledge
- Many scales of acheivement
- Ocassional new breakthrough
- Leads toward new theories

COMMON OPERATION

- Contingent knowledge
- Impersonal organization
- Personal assertion from doubt
- Background resource
- Responsibility, ethics
- On the shoulders of history
- Discipline of transpersonal logic
- Indeterminacy, uncertainty
- Strategic implimentation
- Value and usefulness
- Broad acceptance, not niche
- Testible or demonstrable results
- New contribution to field
- Background and foreground
- Kuhn: New Paradigms
- Circular nature of discovery

Table 9.6: Proposed map for frames of knowledge in architectural education.

Curriculum Areas				
MEANINGFUL EXPERIENCE	ANALYTICAL EVALUATION	DESIGN DECISIONS	ARCHITECTURAL IDEAS	
HISTORY / THEORY / CRITICISM COURSES	TECHNOLOGY / PROGRAMMING / PRACTICE COURSES	STUDIO COURSES	SHARED CURRICULUM	
PARALLEL CONCEPTS	Content (what)	Means (how)	Context (so that)	Ideals (why)
	Substance	Sustenance	Passion	Significance
	Inspiration	Insight	Judgment	Imagination
	Precedent	Integration	Formalization	Connection
	Vocabulary	Tools and protocols	Belief	Abduction
	Engagement	Transformation	Risk and Courage	Assertion
	Domain knowledge	Procedural knowledge	Critical understandings	Structural knowledge
	Emplotment	Equilibrium & flows	Manifestation	Innovation & perturbation
	Heritage	Society	Culture	Civilization
	Knowledge	Work	Resolution	Expression
	Values	Strategy	Satisfaction	Wisdom
	Currency	Intelligence	Aesthetics	The Sublime

TWO SPHERE DOMAINS

COMPARING THE QUADRANTS

Conventional Scientific Inquiry

Native Architectural Inquiry

COMPARING THE QUADRANTS

Native Architectural Inquiry

Real~Ideal
Intelligent~Sublime
Foresight~Immediacy

PATH OF ESSENTIAL TRANSFORMATIONS

ANALYSIS~PROPOSITION~SYNTHESIS
NEW WISDOM VIA ABDUCTIVE CREATIVITY

Nurture knowledge
Serve society
Systematic methods

**DESIGNER'S
GATE**

**RESEARCH
GATE**

NEW WISDOM VIA WORK WITHIN EXISTING KNOWLEDGE
(Sense making and embodied intelligence)

Strategic ~ Lifetime of Learning
Clinical ~ Teaching
Programming & Planning ~ Scholarship of best practices

TRACK OF CONNECTIVE CONFIGURATION

THANK YOU

